

A Study on the Attitude of Tourists towards South Andaman Tourism

*by Easter Baby, Resource Person,
Department of B.Com (Co-op. Mgt.),
M.G. Govt. College, Mayabunder - 744204*

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*G. Eswari, B.Ed. (Commerce),
Department of Commerce,
TG College of Education, Port Blair - 744101*

Introduction :

Tourism has been a major social phenomenon of the societies all along. It is widely acknowledged that tourism is one of the world's largest and fastest-growing industries. India a country with tremendous diversity has a lot to offer in terms of tourism and related activities. In other words heritage site, cultural attractions, beaches, health & wellness like Yoga & Ayurveda, Indian cuisine provides for huge potential for the tourism sector in India. As the Travel and Tourism industry holds tremendous potential for India's economy it is included among the Core Sectors of the Indian Economy.

Tourism began in Port Blair (the capital city as well as a bustling commercial hub) in the late 1970s with the opening of a hotel called Andaman Beach Resort by the Travel Corporation of India Limited. In the 1980s and 1990s, more hotels came up in Port Blair. For about 20 years, until 2000-01, tourism grew at a slow pace. It was limited to lower & middle class and backpack tourists. Now a day majority of the tourists are visiting Andaman & Nicobar Islands and they roamed in and around Port

Blair with main tourist attractions being the Cellular Jail, Mahatma Gandhi Marine National Park (MGMNP) near Wandoor, Ross Island, Chatham Saw Mill, Corbyn's cove beach, Mini Zoo and various museums in the city. Out of the above tourist places; MGMNP remained the most important spot as this park could provide a single platform for viewing tropical flora and fauna of the islands including marine diversity.

Analysis of Data and its Interpretation :

Table No. 1

Distribution of respondents based on ranking analysis

S.No.	Factor	Total score	Mean score	Total
1	Water sports activities	4428	36.9	II
2	Beaches	4443	37.0	I
3	Islands Scenic Beauty (Flora & Fauna)	4239	35.32	III
4	Historical Monuments	3741	31.175	V
5	Museums	3750	31.250	IV
6	Forest trekking	3699	30.825	VI

Source: Primary Data

By applying Garrett's ranking technique, it concluded that the beaches are ranked as an important factor influencing the people to visit the South Andaman District.

Table No. 2

Distribution of respondents based Gender and Level of satisfaction

S.No	Factors	No. of Respondents					Average
		V.G	G	A	Poor	V.P	
1	Male	18	33	6	-	-	57
2	Female	9	53	0	-	-	62
3	Transgender	0	1	0	-	-	1
	Total						

Source: Primary data

Chi-square test on relationship between Gender and Level of satisfaction :

Null hypothesis : There is no relationship between Gender and Level of satisfaction.

Alternative hypothesis : There is a Relationship between Gender and Level of satisfaction.

Relationship between Gender and Level of satisfaction

Type of Test	Calculated value	Table value	Degrees of freedom	Significant level
chi-square	10.13	10.5	8	significant at 5% level

Inference : The calculated value of chi-square value 10.13 is lesser than the table value of the chi-square 10.5 at 5% level of signification with 8 degrees of freedom. It indicates that the null hypothesis accepted, hence there is no significance relationship Gender and Level of satisfaction.

Table No. 3

Distribution of respondents based Age and Level of Satisfaction

S.No.	Factors	No. of Respondents					Total Score
		V.G	G	A	Poor	V.P	
1	below 20	0	6	0	0	0	6
2	21-30	21	18	3	0	0	42
3	31-40	3	27	0	0	0	30
4	41-50	0	18	3	0	0	21
5	above 50	3	18	0	0	0	21
	Total	27	87	6	0	0	120

Source: Primary data

Chi-square test on relationship between Age and Level of Satisfaction :

Null hypothesis : There is no relationship between Age and Level of Satisfaction.

Alternative hypothesis: There is a Relationship between Age and Level of Satisfaction.

Relationship between Age and Level of Satisfaction

Type of Test	Calculated value	Table value	Degrees of freedom	Significant level
chi-square	32.42	26.3	16	significant at 5% level

Inference : The calculated value of chi-square value 32.42 is greater than the table value of the chi-square 26.3 at 5% level of signification with 16 degrees of freedom. It indicates that the null hypothesis rejected hence there is a significance relationship between Age and Level of Satisfaction.

Conclusion :

The Andaman and Nicobar islands have a natural, untapped beauty that is simply enchanting. The turquoise blue sea, talc-like beaches and sheer richness of tropical flora & fauna are the necessary ingredients available for a booming tourism industry. But the concerned authorities should take steps to strengthen the existing infrastructure at tourist destinations and to identify the areas of tourist importance and to develop them with adequate infrastructure for the benefits of the tourists. Though that we can improve the employment potential to the great extent. Thus, tourism is a powerful source of earning more income to the nation. So, tourist destinations should be maintained carefully with pleasant atmosphere to attract more tourists.

References :

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